

THE MECHANICAL RESPONSE OF AN ORTHOTROPIC LAMINATED REINFORCEMENT IN A SYMMETRICAL STRUCTURE

Abdullah Jabar Hussain¹, Zaid Ibrahim Rasool¹, and Zainab S. Al-Khafaji^{2,3*}

¹ Computer Techniques Engineering Department, Al-Mustaqbal University, 51001, Hillah, Iraq.

² New Era and Development in Civil Engineering Research Group, Scientific Research Center, Al-Ayen University, Thi-Qar, 64001, Iraq

³ Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, 43600 UKM Bangi, Selangor, Malaysia. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5450-7312>.

Correspondence: zeinab.radi@alayen.edu.iq; Tel.: (+964 781 812 0132)

ABSTRACT: An experimental and theoretical investigation was carried out to evaluate the effect of the flexural loads on the stress distribution oriented by “0, 45, 45,0” laminates of Kevlar-Epoxy composite. The mechanical response of a new advanced composite material was evaluated by comparing the measured and computed deflection values at the mid-point. The results are compared to other composites that have been built. The use of FEM to analyze composite laminates is limited to stacking sequences with symmetry in the midplane and orientated in the lower half of the laminate, as well as their reflections on the upper half plies. The results of the experimental and FEM show fair agreement.

KEYWORDS: composite, deflection, fiber, laminates, load, orthotropic

1 INTRODUCTION

The invention of composite materials and accompanying design and production techniques are considered one of the most critical advancements in materials history. Composites are versatile materials with exceptional physical and mechanical characteristics that may be tailored to meet specific application requirements. Moreover, several composites have remarkable resistance to abrasion, corrosion, and high temperatures. Mechanical engineers may use design possibilities that are not possible with standard monolithic (unreinforced) materials because of their unique features. Thanks to improvements in composites technology, ceramics may now be utilized in situations where monolithic versions could be more efficient owing to their high strength scatter and poor resistance to thermal and mechanical stress. Complex structures may be created utilizing various composite manufacturing processes, enabling component consolidation and reducing production costs (Al-Zubaidy et al., 2019; Dawood et al., 2020; Sattar, Alaiwi, Radhi, Al-Khafaji, et al., 2023).

A composite material comprises two distinct materials with differing physical and chemical characteristics. Combined, these constituents create a material tailored to a particular purpose (Jabor et al., 2021).

Composites are essential materials in the aerospace industry and various mechanical engineering applications involving electronic packaging, thermal management, machine components, internal combustion engines, and structural elements in vehicles like cars, trains, and planes.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Many researchers presented their research on this field, as follows:

(Broutman & Krock, 1974) They discuss several ideas about composite strength and fracture. They also discuss time-dependent fracture theory and tests, including both long-term and dynamic fracture. All factors affecting the toughness of brittle and ductile matrix composites and the fatigue of polymer—and metal-matrix composites are taken into consideration.

(Agarwal et al., 1981). The book comprehensively covers a number of significant subjects, including mechanics, materials, analysis, fabrication, characterization, and performance. Fundamental ideas are explained in layman's terms, and the subject is gradually broadened while maintaining a balance between mechanics and materials.

Derek (1981) focused on fiber-reinforcing materials supported by matrix materials and utilized in engineering applications as laminates with multiple layers. He shows that the fundamental

benefit of composite materials is their high stiffness-to-weight proportion, which is seen in typical technical applications such as advanced fiber laminated composites like fiberglass, glass epoxy, and Kevlar epoxy (ASTM, 1997; Lee, 2018).

When unidirectional fiber composites are flexed, they may break due to tension, compression, shear, or a combination of these factors (Haleem et al., 2023; Hamza & Radhi, 2023; Hu, 2012; Mohammed & Al-khafaji, 2023; Sattar, Alaiwi, Radhi, & Al-khafaji, 2023b, 2023a). Their research revealed a linear relationship between flexure strength and fiber-volume proportion through an experimental study that is related to constituent qualities, assuming that failure occurs when one of the stresses mentioned previously reaches its limit value as follows.

Where

$\sigma_{1.12}$ = Flexural shear strength.

$\sigma_{1.11(+)}$ = Flexural tensile strength.

$\sigma_{1.11(-)}$ = Flexural compressive strength.

$S_{1.12,S}$ = Longitudinal (interlaminar) shear strength.

$S_{1.11,T}$ = Longitudinal tensile strength.

$S_{1.11,C}$ = Longitudinal compressive strength.

(Daniel et al., 1983) studied the behavior of a multi-layer material under high strain rate conditions and examined the damage development and propagation inside the sample utilizing a mix of experimental and computational techniques.

Research conducted by (Boone et al., 1987) broadened the scope of isotropic analysis utilizing FEM to include orthotropic stiffness, stress-intensities, and orthotropic fracture analysis characteristics. They introduced a straightforward approach to analyzing fracture propagation in orthotropic materials, demonstrating the effectiveness of isoperimetric quarter-point elements in calculating stress intensity factors through orthotropic displacement correlation equations. An illustration of fracture propagation analysis in an orthotropic structure is presented, along with conclusions regarding the impact of anisotropic strength and orthotropic stiffness characteristics.

(Yuan & Miller, 1990) used a new FE model for laminated composite beams. The model has enough degrees of freedom for each lamina's cross-section to deform into a shape that includes up to cubic terms in the thickness coordinate.

(Singh et al., 1990) investigates the bending of anti-symmetric cross-ply plates utilizing one-term approximations for in-plane and transverse displacements. He utilized Ray-leigh-Ritz analysis of non-linear bending of anti-symmetric cross-ply laminates, which produces exact results.

(Zalameda & Smith, 1994) created a nondestructive technique for calculating FVF utilizing a dual inspection approach. The relationship between void volume fractions, matrix, thermal diffusivity, and fiber is given in a one-dimensional heat flow model where the void volume fraction is calculated utilizing ultrasound. In order to quantify thermal diffusivity quantitatively, a phase lag approach is utilized. The composite plates utilized for these measurements have different FVFs. With values ranging from 003-007 cm^2/sec , diffusivity measurements revealed a nonlinear relationship between FVF and observed diffusivity. Within the region to be destructively tested, frequency-dependent relative attenuation ultrasonic measurements were made in addition to the heat data. According to the findings, porosity and attenuation are roughly correlated.

According to a study (Meyers & Chawla, 2008), the orientation of the fibers plays a crucial role in the strength of a composite material. Strength peaks when aligned with the fibers and decreases when perpendicular to them.

Matrix cracking is a topic that they discuss in laminated composite materials. The factors affecting the start and progression of internal damage under various loadings are discussed. A fracture mechanics technique or a probabilistic failure strength theory is used to predict additional cracking. Some researchers use continuum damage mechanics to simulate the behavior of the broken laminate. When a layer delaminates in layered materials, the layer bends and, if the stress is strong enough, can trigger progressive layer breakdown, resulting in a small zone that spreads as a bending fracture. (Pasternak & Dyskin, 1999) A disinclination's moment of stress decays according to the inverse square root of the crack's root distance (r).

(Wang et al., 2002), the first-order shear deformation theory (FSDT) is utilized, and the displacement shape functions are created by the reproducing kernel approximating to meet consistency constraints. The fundamental boundary conditions are applied utilizing a single kernel approach. Numerical instances with different boundary conditions are solved to show that the suggested technique is valid. Comparing findings with precise and established solutions in the literature indicates that the meshless technique

provides an efficient solution for laminated composite plates.

(Huang & Li, 2004) This study uses the moving least square differential quadrature (MLSDQ) technique, which is based on the first-order shear deformation theory, the bending and buckling analysis of antisymmetric thick laminates. Within each region of effect, the centered moving least square (MLS) approximation is utilized to assume the plate's displacement and rotation components separately. The nodal partial derivatives are computed quickly together with the MLS nodal shape functions, and these two computations result in the weighting coefficients. The accuracy, stability, and convergence of the MLSDQ approach are examined utilizing numerical examples. The effects of node irregularity, support size, and the order of the entire basis functions on numerical accuracy are investigated—computed displacements, stresses, and critical buckling loads for various laminated.

The study by (El Messiry, 2013) explores the utilization of epoxy and fiber as lamina to create composite laminates with specific directional characteristics. Characteristics of composites are determined based on the characteristics of the epoxy and fiber, utilizing the rule of mixtures. The fiber volume fraction is crucial in determining the overall characteristics. This work determines the value of the fiber volume fraction by considering fibrous structure constituent, random fiber, yarns, or fabric.

(Oleiwi et al., 2014) Develop a polymer matrix composite material by hand lay-up, utilizing an unsaturated polyester resin matrix and natural jute fibers of varying volume fractions as reinforcement (3 percent, 4 percent, 5 percent, 6 percent). To investigate the impact of specific jute fiber volume fractions on the bending characteristics, numerical experiments utilizing the finite element technique (Ansys 11 program) were performed. According to the findings of this experimental study, increasing the volume proportion of jute fibers increases the bending modulus. For both experimental and numerical studies, the values of deflection and max. Strain falls while flexural strength and shear stress values rise as the volume percent of jute fibers increases.

(Vescovini & Dozio, 2015) This study analyzes and presents the buckling of thin and thick composite plates under biaxial stresses and a unified Levy-type solution approach. Two opposite edges of the plates are supported, and any combination of simply supported, clamped, and free conditions are applied to the two remaining sides. A variable-kinematic technique is utilized to formulate the issue, which has the benefit of automatically

handling theories of varied orders. Layer-wise theories and comparable single-layer theories are both considered. The governing equilibrium equations are precisely solved utilizing the Lévy-type approach and are analytically derived from the Principle of Virtual Displacements (PVD). Comparisons with results from the literature, including exact 3D solutions, show how accurate the predictions are. A complete set of benchmark outcomes is offered.

(Sezgin & Berkalp, 2017) composites made of four-ply jute, carbon, and E-glass fabric reinforcement, and their hybridized versions are produced. Vacuum infusion technology creates nine composite laminates with various stacking arrangements. The fiber weight and volume proportions in the laminate system are first calculated to comprehend the composites' structure. Additionally, sample void fractions are calculated utilizing theoretical and experimental densities of the composite samples to investigate the effect of the amount of fiber content on the void fraction. The mechanical characteristics (tensile strength, impact strength) of composite laminates and the effects of hybridizing jute fabric-reinforced polyester composite with E-glass fabric and carbon fabric are studied. The findings of this inquiry indicate that.

(Sathish et al., 2017) investigated the impact of volume fraction on the mechanical and physical characteristics of flax and bamboo fiber-reinforced hybrid epoxy composites, including tensile, flexural, impact, interlaminar shear strength, void content, and water absorption. Compression molding techniques have created hybrid composites with flax and bamboo fiber reinforcement. Hybrid composites were created utilizing various fiber volume fractions. SEM examination of the hybrid composite materials was carried out to examine the internal structure of the fractured surfaces and the bonding behavior of the materials. By utilizing FTIR measurement, the impact of chemically treating flax and bamboo fibers was confirmed. The results showed that the tensile, impact, flexural, and ILSS are max. For 40:0 (flax: bamboo) hybrid composites. The void content decreased for 20:20 (flax: bamboo) composites due to tightly packed flax fiber and more compatibility with the epoxy resin.

(Ali & Anjaneyulu, 2018) Determine if unidirectional carbon fiber is suitable for use in the design of a composite suspension system by considering the impact of fiber orientation and matrix volume fractions.

(Younis et al., 2018) examined how Nano silica particles affected specimen composite material's

wear behavior test results for ultimate tensile strength, impact strength, fracture toughness, and shore D hardness. The hand-lay-up technique is utilized to manufacture specimens made from unsaturated polyester resin matrix reinforcement with a 4% weight fraction glass fiber (chopped/woven) mat and 1%, 3%, and 5% weight fraction of Nano silica particles. The mean size of the Nano-silica particles employed in this investigation is (less than 45 nm). The outcomes revealed that the specimen's mechanical characteristics, including ultimate tensile strength, were superior (up to +4% woven glass fiber +5% Nano SiO₂).

(David Müzel et al., 2020) Provide FEM in order to model composite materials; this effort will focus on the material's qualities, failure criteria, types of elements, and primary application fields.

2.1 Procedure

Five stages were done in the present work to introduce the research in acceptable form, which are as follows:

1. Advanced composites by lay-up technique, which include 4 plies-Kevlar-epoxy (12% Vf, (0,45,45,0), one-ply unidirectional Kevlar-epoxy (12% Vf), 4-ply woven fabric (cross-ply), Kevlar –epoxy (12% Vf) and resin made of epoxy without any fiber.
2. Experiments are conducted to study the mechanical flexural response utilizing a 3-point test.
3. A c-scan image is utilized to evaluate the failure mode.
4. 3-D FEM by ANSYS and a structural analysis program are utilized to model the mechanical response.
5. Finally, the experimental results are compared with those obtained from ANSYS.

3 FIBER REINFORCED MATERIAL

These materials are created by embedding a softer or ductile matrix with continuous or discontinuous fibers of a tough substance. They can be thought of as homogeneous laminated orthotropic materials.

Several plies of unidirectional or woven fabric composites are layered at various angles relative to the laminate's x-axis to form the laminated composite material, as shown in Fig.(1-a).

Fig. 1. a) Fiber reinforcement composite (0, 45, 45, 0); b) unidirectional layer

For the case of equal ply thickness, the stacking sequence can be described by simply listing the ply orientation (θ) from the bottom to the top. The subscript "T" means sequence accounts for the total number of layers such as [0,45,45,0]_T

3.1 Maximum Fiber Stress

When a beam of homogeneous elastic material is tested in flexure as a simple beam supported at two locations and loaded at the mid-span, the maximum stress in the outer fibers occurs at the mid-span.

$$\sigma_{\max} = \frac{3PL}{2bh^2} \quad (2)$$

where,

σ_{\max} = the stress in outer fibers at the mid-span (N/m²)

P= the load at a certain point on the load-deflection curve (N)

L= support span (m)

b= width of the tested beam(m)

h= thickness of the tested beam(m)

However, the flexural strength is equal to the max. Stress in the outer fibers at the moment of break, i.e., $\sigma_{\text{flex}} = \sigma_{\max}$.

After the modules of elasticity, the tangent modulus of elasticity is the proportion of stress to the corresponding strain inside the elastic limit. It is computed by drawing the load-deflection curve's sharpest beginning straight-line part and then applying equation (2) for the orthotropic composite. If the shear deformation is ignored (Lee, 2018), yield.

$$E_b = \frac{L^3}{4bh^3} M \quad (3)$$

Or,

$$E_b = \frac{PL^3}{4bh^3\delta} \quad (4)$$

Where,

E_b = Modulus of elasticity in bending (N/m²)

M = Slope of the tangent to the initial straight line portion of the load-deflection curve.

δ = Max. Deflection at the mid-span (m).

However, shear stress will develop between the outer support and the applied load if shear deformation is considered. Therefore, the max. Shear stress τ_{\max} in case of three-point loading (Clyne & Hull, 2019) is given by:

$$\tau_{\max} = \frac{b}{2L} \sigma_{\max} \quad (5)$$

3.2 Three Point Bend Test

The load is applied at the center point of the beam in the three-point bend test, and the bending moment (M) increases from the two extremities to the max. At the center point, as shown in Fig. 2. In this case, the moment might be calculated as:

$$M = \frac{PL}{4} \tag{6}$$

Hence, the moment of inertia for a rectangular beam is:

$$I = \frac{bh^3}{12} \tag{7}$$

Then, the maximum stress in the outer layer (y=h/2) can be obtained from equation (2) above.

Fig. 2. Application of loads and bending moment diagram for the three-point bending.

The elastic normal stress distribution through the thickness when the beam is bent can be shown in Figure 3

Fig. 3. Normal stresses along a section of beam for linearity elastic (Singh et al., 1990)

4 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

The following steps are described in the practical section of this work:

1. A special rig is manufactured with 2000 holes of 1 mm in diameter to produce up to 4-4-ply multidirectional reinforcing composite, as illustrated in Fig 4

Fig. 4. Rig for unidirectional and multidirectional fiber packing

The holes are arranged to get rectangular packing with the exact distance between each pair in the x-direction (Agarwal et al., 2017), as illustrated in Fig.5.

Fig. 5. a) one side of the rig; b) rectangular arrangement

To continue with the experimental activity, volume percentage must be computed because composites comprise two phases: reinforcement and matrix. The volume proportion of reinforcement and matrix determines the mechanical characteristics of these composites. Reinforcing materials such as fiber, particles, and whiskers can all be employed. The fiber volume fraction may be calculated utilizing the fiber weight fraction, and the other mechanical characteristics can be calculated utilizing the fiber volume fraction. The stiffness and strength of a composite laminate can be improved by increasing the volume fraction of fibers in the laminate because it assumes that the fibers are touching and ignores any voids that may exist in the cured laminate, the max. volume fraction of fibers is a theoretical estimate. The volume fraction can be determined as follows (Agarwal et al., 2017):

$$V_f = \frac{\pi}{4} \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2 \tag{8}$$

$$S = 2r \left\{ \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{4V_f}} - 1 \right\} \tag{9}$$

Where “r” is the radius of the fiber
And 2R is the center-to-center spacing of the fibers

1. Prepare along fibers of Kevlar “49” from woven fiber cloth.
2. Weave 4 plies as (0,45,45,0) per the stacking sequence in Fig.6.
3. Mix 3:1 Epoxy Cy223 with hardener Hy 956.
4. Pour the mixture into a rig, then leave it for 24 hrs. at room temperature.
5. Please put it in the controlled furnace at 60 C⁰ for about 16 hrs. and leave it cold for about 24 hrs. as recommended by MBT company.
6. Prepare specimens for the flexural test as per ASTM D790.
7. Flexural strength is obtained, and the relation between load and deflection is drawn as a result of the three-point test at two classes.
 - Load bearing on first ply and transfer to other.
 - Load bearing on the four plies directly.

9. Prepare a one-ply unidirectional lamina composite from Kevlar-Epoxy $V_f = 12\%$ following steps 3.5, 6, 7, and then repeat step 8.

10. Produce another rig to prepare 4-ply cross-ply woven fabric from Kevlar – Epoxy $V_f = 12\%$ following steps (4, 5, 6,7,8) mentioned above.

Prepare lamina made from epoxy resin and repeat the procedure in steps 7 and 8

5 FINITE ELEMENT TECHNIQUE

The stress and deflection fields are obtained using the ANSYS version 5,4 F.E. programs (Lee, 2018).

The material's tensile and flexural characteristics have been considered orthotropic. From a modeling perspective, composites are more challenging to model than isotropic materials because extra care must be taken in defining the attributes of the orientations of the many layers. After all, each layer may have different orthotropic characteristics.

When constructing the composite model, focus on the following aspects of the current study.

1. Choosing the suitable element type (solid 46)
2. Defining the layer configuration as in Fig.6.
3. Specifying failure criteria (Von misses).
4. Adherence to modeling and post-processing guidelines.

Fig. 6. Ansys lay plot display for symmetric orthotropic material.

6 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Figure 7 shows the load-deflection relationship for two types of flexural loading composites (Kevlar-epoxy 0, 45, and 45,0). The first load was applied laterally (perpendicular to the first ply) to the specimens. In contrast, the other load was applied perpendicular to the cross-section, i.e., to all

plies of the arrangement. It also shows a fair agreement between the theoretical (F.E.M results) and practical.

Fig. 7. Load-deflection curve Kevlar-49 reinforced epoxy (0, 45, 45, 0) 3-point test.

The result of FEM in the first situation, the weight is passed from one layer to the next. In contrast, in the second case, the material with all layers supports the load, as illustrated in Fig.7, increasing the carrying load.

The load-deflection relationship for single-layer specimens is shown in Fig.8 (Kevlar- Epoxy - 12 percent V_f). It depicts the nature of the specimen's loading and unloading and the residual strain after the load has been removed, which must be recovered after a period of time.

Fig. 8. Flexural Strength and residual strength for one-ply composite (Kevlar-epoxy 12%Vf) 3-point test longitudinal load.

Fig. 9 shows the same type of specimen with a single layer. However, the fibers are oriented by 900 to the axis of the specimen during loading and unloading, and the same residual strain is indicated with the higher load. There are no remarkable differences in the bending performance with the indicated load.

Fig. 9. Flexural Strength and residual strength for only ply composite (Kevlar-epoxy 12% Vf) 3-point test transfer load.

Fig.10 shows the load-deflection for the specimens made of four layers reinforced with woven (cross-ply) Kevlar where the fibers are parallel, and at 90°, which is the same as one-layer specimens, the higher residual strain was observed after the load removal. The specimen, during unloading, exhibited distributed unsteady performance, resulting in a scatter of readings. Also, the behavior differed from the single ply in the relation being non-linear and much lower deflection values, which is due to the higher stiffness of the specimen compared with those of the single layer, as shown in Table 1.

Fig. 10. Flexural Strength and residual strength for cross-ply composite (Kevlar-epoxy 12% Vf) 3-point test.

Fig. 11 shows the load-deflection for resin only. The higher deflection was noticed as expected for the same load, and the higher residual strain was observed after load removal.

Fig. 11. Flexural Strength Residual strength for Resin (epoxy cy223+hardner HY356-3 point test).

Fig 12 shows the scanning electron micrograph of the failed nature of the specimen (0,45,45,0). It clearly shows the failed fiber of the specimen as per the experimental work.

Fig. 12. Scanning electron micrograph of failed specimen (0, 45, 45, 0) Kevlar 49-epoxy

Table 1: Flexural strength and max. Strain for some typical composite and resin.

Type	Failure load N	Max. deflection mm	Max. strain mm/mm	Flexural strength MPa
Cross-ply (woven)	700	3.4	0.0159	258.460
Resin (Epoxy)	550	3	0.0288	103.125
(0,45,45,0) first case	3000	9.4	0.0202	192.300
(0,45,45,0) second case	3200	9	0.0226	189.140

7 CONCLUSION

The following conclusions were drawn from the above figures and observations made during the experimental study. The behavior of the current material, four plies with Kevlar fibers oriented at (0,45,45, 0), differed from that of the other materials reviewed and their outcomes.

The current material reaction to the load is not immediate, but it does have a time-based delay.

Under the same load, the material has a considerable deflection.

As the deflection is passed from one layer to the next, it takes specific pathways that are not always perpendicular to the beam's axis, and the deflection rotates as observed throughout the experiment, which is because force is resolved to each orientated fiber.

In the second case (load perpendicular to all plies), the new material failed due to mixed modes of longitudinal-compressive, transverse-

compressive, and bending failures. In contrast, in the first case, the material failed due to compression at the upper layers and tension at the lower layers, resulting in hairiness phenomena in the Kevlar.

The response of multi-layered multi-directional composites is evaluated as a function of ply fiber orientation and stacking sequence.

FEM predicts longitudinal strain. In the first case, lateral loading in a (0,45,45,0) orthotropic construction composite deviates significantly from experimental results. In contrast, transverse strain in the second case for the same material compares favorably with experimental results, indicating that fiber direction and type of loading play a significant role in the load-bearing capacity of a multi-layered, multi-directional laminate.

Laminate thickness, stacking sequence, lamination structure (number of layers), and nature of loading all affect the amount and variance of deflections of Kevlar reinforcing Epoxy.

A significant finding of the current study is that material (0,45,45,0) composite is more sensitive to bending stress than others, as shown in Table (1). The [(woven (cross-ply))] stacking is stiffer and has higher flexural strength, failing at a lower strain, whereas the material (0,45,45,0) composite failed at the highest strain and had lower flexural strength.

The failure mode is exhibited in specimens with unidirectional fibers in the fiber itself, but failure was limited to the surface layer only in the other types.

8 REFERENCES

- Agarwal, B. D., Broutman, L. J., & Bert, C. W. (1981). *Analysis and performance of fiber composites*.
- Agarwal, B. D., Broutman, L. J., & Chandrashekhara, K. (2017). *Analysis and Performance of Fiber Composites*.
- Al-Zubaidy, B., Radhi, N. S., & Al-Khafaji, Z. S. (2019). Study the effect of thermal impact on the modelling of (titanium-titania) functionally graded materials by using finite element analysis. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology*, 1.
- Ali, M. I., & Anjaneyulu, J. (2018). Effect of fiber-matrix volume fraction and fiber orientation on the design of composite suspension system. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 455(1), 12104.
- ASTM, S. (1997). Standard test methods for flexural properties of unreinforced and reinforced plastics and electrical insulating materials. ASTM D790. *Annual Book of ASTM Standards*.
- Boone, T. J., Wawrzynek, P. A., & Ingraffea, A. R. (1987). Finite element modelling of fracture propagation in orthotropic materials. *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 26(2), 185–201.
- Broutman, L. J., & Krock, R. H. (1974). *Composite Materials: Engineering applications of composites* (Vol. 3). Academic Press.
- Clyne, T. W., & Hull, D. (2019). *An introduction to composite materials*. Cambridge University Press.
- Daniel, I. M., Whitney, J. M., & Pipes, R. B. (1983). *Experimental Mechanics of Fiber Reinforced Composite Materials: Fourth volume in the SESA Monograph Series. Experimental Techniques*, 7(3), 25.
- David Müzel, S., Bonhin, E. P., Guimarães, N. M., & Guidi, E. S. (2020). Application of the finite element method in the analysis of composite materials: A review. *Polymers*, 12(4), 818.
- Dawood, N. M., Radhi, N. S., & Al-khafaji, Z. S. (2020). *Investigation Corrosion and Wear Behavior of Nickel-Nano Silicon Carbide on Stainless Steel 316L*. 1002, 33–43. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/MSF.1002.33>
- Derek, H. (1981). *An introduction to composite materials*. Cambridge University Press.
- El Messiry, M. (2013). Theoretical analysis of natural fiber volume fraction of reinforced composites. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 52(3), 301–306.
- Haleem, A. H., Radhi, N. S., & Jaber, N. T. (2023). A STUDY ON STAINLESS STEEL 316L UTILIZING SINGLE-STEP ANODIZATION AND A DC SPUTTERING PLASMA OF SILVER COATING TO IMPROVE CORROSION RESISTANCE. *Academic Journal of Manufacturing Engineering*, 21(4), 1–10.
- Hamza, S. A., & Radhi, N. S. (2023). Composite Coating Using (Hap-Nano Silver) By Macro Arc Oxidation Procedures Was Used To Study the in-Vivo Properties of Titanium Substrate. *Academic Journal of Manufacturing Engineering*, 21(1), 65–71.
- Hu, N. (2012). *Composites and their applications*. BoD–Books on Demand.
- Huang, Y. Q., & Li, Q. (2004). Bending and buckling analysis of antisymmetric laminates using the moving least square differential quadrature method. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 193(33–35), 3471–3492.
- Jabor, M., Radh, N. S., Al-kinani, M. A., & Al-khafaji, Z. S. (2021). Optimization of Electro less of Nickel base coating for Cermet Cutting Tools

- Substrate. *Journal of Mechanical Engineering Research and Developments*, 44(3), 30–40.
- Lee, H.-H. (2018). *Finite element simulations with ANSYS Workbench 18*. SDC publications.
- Meyers, M. A., & Chawla, K. K. (2008). *Mechanical behavior of materials*. Cambridge University Press.
- Mohammed, E., & Al-khafaji, Z. (2023). Effect of Surface Treatments by Ultrasonic on NiTi Biomaterials. *ACADEMIC JOURNAL OF MANUFACTURING ENGINEERING*, 21(3), 1–6.
- Olewi, J. K., Alwan, M. K., & Hamad, Q. A. (2014). Numerically and experimentally studying of some mechanical properties of the polyester matrix composite material reinforced by jute fibers. *Engineering and Technology Journal*, 32(9 Part A), 2235–2247.
- Pasternak, E., & Dyskin, A. (1999). Semi-infinite bending crack in layered materials. Cosserat continuum approach. *SEMI-INFINITE BENDING CRACK IN LAYERED MATERIALS. COSSERAT CONTINUUM APPROACH*, 135–142.
- Sathish, S., Kumaresan, K., Prabhu, L., & Vigneshkumar, N. (2017). Experimental investigation on volume fraction of mechanical and physical properties of flax and bamboo fibers reinforced hybrid epoxy composites. *Polymers and Polymer Composites*, 25(3), 229–236.
- Sattar, S., Alaiwi, Y., Radhi, N. S., & Al-khafaji, Z. (2023a). Numerical Simulation for Effect of Composite Coating (TiO₂ + SiO₂) Thickness on Steam Turbine Blades Thermal and Stress Distribution. *ACADEMIC JOURNAL OF MANUFACTURING ENGINEERING*, 21(4).
- Sattar, S., Alaiwi, Y., Radhi, N. S., & Al-khafaji, Z. (2023b). NUMERICAL SIMULATION FOR EFFECT OF COMPOSITE COATING (TIO₂ + SIO₂) THICKNESS ON STEAM TURBINE BLADES THERMAL AND STRESS DISTRIBUTION. *Academic Journal of Manufacturing Engineering*, 21(4), 86–99.
- Sattar, S., Alaiwi, Y., Radhi, N. S., Al-Khafaji, Z., Al-Hashimi, O., Alzahrani, H., & Yaseen, Z. M. (2023). Corrosion reduction in steam turbine blades using nano-composite coating. *Journal of King Saud University-Science*, 35(8), 102861. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jksus.2023.102861>
- Sezgin, H., & Berkalp, O. B. (2017). The effect of hybridization on significant characteristics of jute/glass and jute/carbon-reinforced composites. *Journal of Industrial Textiles*, 47(3), 283–296.
- Singh, G., Raju, K. K., Rao, G. V., & Iyengar, N. G. R. (1990). Non-linear bending of antisymmetric cross-ply plates. *Composite Structures*, 14(4), 359–371.
- Vescovini, R., & Dozio, L. (2015). Exact refined buckling solutions for laminated plates under uniaxial and biaxial loads. *Composite Structures*, 127, 356–368.
- Wang, J., Liew, K. M., Tan, M. J., & Rajendran, S. (2002). Analysis of rectangular laminated composite plates via FSDT meshless method. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, 44(7), 1275–1293.
- Younis, S., Olewi, J. K., & Mohammed, R. A. (2018). Some mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites reinforced by nano silica particles and glass fibers. *Engineering and Technology Journal*, 36(12), 1283–1289.
- Yuan, F.-G., & Miller, R. E. (1990). A higher-order finite element for laminated beams. *Composite Structures*, 14(2), 125–150.
- Zalameda, J. N., & Smith, B. T. (1994). Measurement of composite fiber volume fraction using thermal and ultrasonic inspection techniques. In *Nondestructive Characterization of Materials VI* (pp. 741–748). Springer.